
GRAPHIA WP2

QLever Evaluation Report

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Benchmark conducted on custom synthetic GoTriple KG with 155M triples

QLever Git Hash 958d01 (Build: 2026-02-24)

Virtuoso 07.20.3233

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results of a systematic benchmark of QLever against Virtuoso on the GoTriple knowledge graph (155M triples, ~10M named graphs), conducted as part of GRAPHIA WP2 T2.2. The evaluation addresses a concrete architectural question: can QLever replace or complement Virtuoso as the default RDF backend for the SSH KG? The benchmark covers 8 areas: (1) ingestion & indexing performance, (2) dataset validation, (3) SPARQL 1.1 compliance, (4) named graph management, (5) federation, (6) live update feasibility, (7) concurrent load and memory stability, and (8) update persistence and durability.

To guide the final architectural decision, four potential outcomes were defined for QLever:

1. **Secondary Engine:** Keep it as a complementary analytical tool alongside Virtuoso.
2. **R&D Only:** Maintain it strictly for benchmarking and evaluation.
3. **Abandon:** Discontinue its integration entirely.
4. **Primary Engine:** Promote it as the sole default backend from day one (replacing Virtuoso entirely).

Finding: The evidence collected in this benchmark supports Outcome #4 as the technically preferred option for the current phase of GRAPHIA. QLever is production-ready as the primary RDF backend for the read-heavy, batch-consolidated operating model evaluated in this benchmark. It outperforms Virtuoso on 80% of tested query patterns, safely handles 100 concurrent updates within the tested batch window, and demonstrates a 5x ingestion speed advantage (indexing 155M triples in ~3.7 minutes compared to Virtuoso's ~15 minutes). Crucially, its massive speed and indexing efficiency also position it as the ideal candidate to power the "Graph as a Service" (GaaS) intermediate materialisation layer for the project's wider Federated Gateway.

Risks & Mitigation: This architectural transition must be managed with caution. QLever remains an actively developed academic project, lacking the decades of enterprise hardening of Virtuoso. Its initial setup is complex and highly sensitive to hardware configurations, requiring expert tuning. The most significant architectural question raised during this evaluation was update persistence: QLever's delta triples are held in memory and lost on ungraceful restarts. This is not a blocker. Test 8.8 confirms that qllever rebuild-index consolidates all delta triples into a fully optimized on-disk index in 23 seconds for 155M triples - fast enough for hourly or per-batch scheduling. After a rebuild, updated data is handled with the same performance as data indexed from scratch. This implies a log-and-consolidate ingestion model (batch durability), not a fully transactional RDF database model.

The practical production pattern for GoTriple is a single-engine architecture. The Data Acquisition Platform (DAP) writes deltas via SPARQL Update and maintains a durable source log. At scheduled intervals, qllever rebuild-index consolidates all pending updates. In the event of a crash between rebuilds, the DAP replays from the durable log, restoring consistency natively. **Under this model, Virtuoso is not required as the primary backend under the proposed architecture.**

A validation phase on real GoTriple production data is recommended before final production lock-in.

Context

The GRAPHIA project aims to build a federated Knowledge Graph for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Within Work Package 2 (WP2), the technical architecture and deployment infrastructure for the central GoTriple Knowledge Graph and the wider Federated Gateway are being defined.

Initially, the technical architecture ([Deliverable D2.2](#)) proposed [Virtuoso](#) as the default RDF backend. However, the specific requirements of the SSH KG, namely highly performant analytical queries, deep pagination for user interfaces, and large-scale graph traversal, prompted the WP2 technical team to explore alternative solutions. [QLever](#), an actively developed and highly optimized SPARQL engine, was identified as a strong candidate.

This document presents the methodology, empirical results, and architectural conclusions of a comprehensive stress-test benchmark comparing QLever and Virtuoso. Operating on a 155-million triple synthetic dataset, the goal of this report is to provide the Technical Coordination Board with concrete evidence to definitively guide the database technology selection for both the GoTriple KG production deployment and the Federated Gateway's mediation layer.

1. Benchmark protocol

1.1 Setup

Overview

Both engines were deployed in isolated Docker containers on identical infrastructure, sharing no resources. The GoTriple synthetic KG (GoTriple-Bench v1) was ingested in full by both engines prior to any benchmark run.

Parameter	QLever	Virtuoso
Image	adfreiburg/qllever:latest	tenforce/virtuoso:latest
Version	Git Hash 958d01 (2026-02-24)	OpenLink 07.20.3233
Memory	5G (-m 5G)	Default
Index	6-permutation (SPO/SOP/PSO/POS/OSP/OP S)	B-tree + quad store
SPARQL endpoint	http://qllever:7001/sparql	http://virtuoso:8890/sparql

Infrastructure & resource allocation

The evaluation was performed on a high-specification macOS environment (Apple Silicon) with the following constraints to simulate a robust production node:

- Host Memory: 64 GB Unified Memory.
- Docker VM Allocation: The Docker Desktop Linux VM was specifically configured with 40 GB of RAM and 14 CPUs to allow for high-concurrency indexing.
- Storage: NVMe SSD (measured at ~200 MB/s during ingestion).

Orchestration & bootstrap (init.sh)

A custom orchestration script ensures a "Clean-Room" environment for each run:

- Memory-safe indexing: QLever indexing is restricted to a 24 GB RAM limit to ensure stability.
- Zero-copy ingestion: The environment uses Hard Links (ln) between the host and the Virtuoso mount, allowing for "Zero-Copy" loading without doubling disk usage.
- Stateless rebuilds: The script enforces a full cleanup of local persisted states before each run to prevent bias from previous runs.

Service orchestration (docker-compose.yml)

The services are managed as a unit using Docker Compose, including healthcheck synchronization to ensure the engines are fully ready before the benchmark starts.

Reproducibility & Source code

The complete benchmark environment, including the dataset generator, orchestration scripts (init.sh), and the evaluation Jupyter Notebook, is open-sourced and available on GitLab:

https://gitlab.operas-eu.org/graphia/qllever/-/tree/eval/evaluation?ref_type=heads

1.2 Synthetic dataset specification

To ensure a stress-test environment that reflects the future scale and complexity of the GoTriple SSH Knowledge Graph, a custom synthetic dataset was generated using the GoTriple-Bench v1 generator. This approach allows for controlled cardinality and the evaluation of the engines against the [exact semantic model defined in Deliverable D2.2](#).

Data generation logic

The dataset was generated in **N-Quads (.nq) format** to support the evaluation of Named Graph management. The generation logic follows a "Provenance-First"

architecture: every entity is assigned its own unique Named Graph, containing both its metadata and its technical provenance.

Ontology mapping

The generator implements the multi-ontology approach required for GRAPHIA, mapping synthetic entities to the following namespaces:

- **Core metadata:** schema.org (CreativeWork, Dataset, MediaObject, Project)
- **Scientific citations:** cito:cites (Citation graph)
- **Identity & profiles:** foaf:Person and datacite:Identifier (ORCID)s)
- **Annotations (WP4):** oa:Annotation and skos:exactMatch to Wikidata
- **Provenance:** prov:wasGeneratedBy and dcterms:created

Realism vs. randomness

While the titles and dates are randomized, the graph topology is realistic:

- **Connectivity:** Authors are linked to multiple documents, and documents are linked to projects, creating a dense web of joins.
- **Vocabulary constraints:** All licenses, disciplines, and access conditions are drawn from the controlled vocabularies defined in D2.2 Section 3.3.2.
- **WP4 Simulation:** 50% of documents include schema:mentions and corresponding oa:Annotation nodes to simulate the output of the GRAPHIA WP4 pipelines.

Quantitative Breakdown

The generated graph consists of **155,554,861 triples** distributed across **10,110,005 named graphs**. The distribution of entities was calculated to simulate a "production-ready" SSH repository:

Total triples	155,554,861	155,557,362

Named graphs	N/A (enum. limit)	10,110,005
Namespaces verified	schema:, cito:	schema:, cito:
Triple delta	2,501 vs Virtuoso	reference

Entity type	Class	Count	Key properties
Documents	schema:CreativeWork	8,000,000	Headlines, Dates, Licenses, Authors
Datasets	schema:Dataset	1,000,000	Access conditions, Disciplines
Profiles	foaf:Person	500,000	ORCID identifiers, Names
Media	schema:MediaObject	500,000	Audio/Video research outputs
Annotations	oa:Annotation	~4,000,000	NER results, mentions, target links
Citations	cito:cites	314,745	Intra-graph citation links

1.3 Methodology

- All queries run cold (cache cleared via ?cmd=clear-cache before each timed test)
- Performance tests repeated 3 times and averaged to reduce noise

- Timeouts set to 120s for standard queries, 30s for stress tests
- SPARQL Update tests use dedicated named graphs to avoid index contamination
- Federation tests target the live OpenCitations SPARQL endpoint (sparql.opencitations.net/index)
- Concurrency tests use Python ThreadPoolExecutor with 5 readers + 3 writers simultaneously

1.4 Scope and limitations

This benchmark evaluates QLever on a synthetic dataset. Real GoTriple data may exhibit different cardinality distributions. The citation graph covers only 150k of 8M documents (per D2.2 generator spec), which bounds citation query results. Named graph enumeration at 10M scale exposed a QLever client-side OOM on `COUNT(DISTINCT ?g)`, documented as a known limitation.

2. Results by category

2.1 Ingestion & indexing performance

The ingestion phase for 155,554,861 triples exposed a significant divergence in architectural efficiency between the two engines.

QLever Indexing

QLever utilizes a specialized qllever-index builder. The setup required fine-tuning the Docker entrypoint and memory constraints (24 GB RAM limit) to ensure stability during the 6-permutation build.

- Duration: 03:41 (From 15:02:59 to 15:06:40).
- Peak Parsing Speed: 2.8 M/s.
- Conversion Speed: 39.8 M/s.
- Result: A highly optimized on-disk 6-permutation index ready for sub-second analytical queries.

Virtuoso Bulk Loading

Virtuoso uses a traditional SQL-based bulk loader (`rdf_loader_run`). While the setup is more "user-friendly" as it uses standard SQL commands, it is bound by the overhead of B-Tree index updates.

- Duration: ~15:00.
- Efficiency: ~5x slower than QLever.

Performance Summary

Engine	Total time	Avg. Throughput	Setup complexity
QLever	3m 41s	~1.1 M/s	High (requires compiler tuning)
Virtuoso	~15m 01s	~0.17 M/s	High (requires specific configurations)

2.2 SPARQL 1.1 Compliance (Section 3)

Both engines pass the core SPARQL 1.1 compliance suite, with notable differences in two areas.

Test	QLever	Virtuoso	Notes
3.1 FILTER / BOUND / String ops	PASS	PASS	QLever 3.1s vs Virtuoso 14.9s
3.2 OPTIONAL patterns	PASS	PASS	QLever 2.7s vs Virtuoso 6.8s
3.3 GROUP BY / HAVING	PASS	PASS	QLever 0.06s vs Virtuoso 0.31s
3.4 ORDER BY / LIMIT / OFFSET	PASS	FAIL	Virtuoso: SR353 limit at OFFSET 10k
3.5 Property paths (cito:cites+)	PASS	PASS*	Virtuoso requires OPTION TRANSITIVE
3.6 VALUES / BIND	PASS	PARTIAL	BIND arithmetic silent fail on QLever 3.6.2

Key finding: Virtuoso's hard limit of 10,100 rows on ORDER BY + OFFSET (test 3.4, error SR353) is a production blocker for any paginated API built on top of the SSH KG. QLever handles deep pagination efficiently, with OFFSET 10,000 returning in 0.008s vs Virtuoso's outright rejection.

Virtuoso's non-standard OPTION TRANSITIVE syntax for property paths (test 3.5) requires engine-specific query variants to be maintained in application code, a maintenance burden that QLever eliminates with standard SPARQL 1.1.

2.3 Analytical Query Performance (Sections 2 - 4)

QLever demonstrates consistent performance advantages on aggregation and graph-intensive queries, which represent the dominant workload class in the SSH KG.

Query pattern	QLever	Virtuoso	Factor
Class counts (2.1, 6 classes)	26.7s	46.6s	1.7x faster
Vocab check (2.2, 155M triples)	1.3s	61.8s (timeout)	>47x faster
Graph distribution (2.4, 10M graphs)	7.7s	TIMEOUT	Virtuoso fails
Cross-graph join (4.5)	24.3s	TIMEOUT (62s)	Virtuoso fails
GRAPH + FILTER + OPTIONAL (4.6)	6.0s	TIMEOUT (60s)	Virtuoso fails
GROUP BY / HAVING (3.3)	0.06s	0.31s	5x faster
ORDER BY OFFSET 1,000 (3.4)	0.013s	4.3s	330x faster

Named graph operations at scale are where the performance gap is most decisive. Virtuoso times out on 3 of 7 named graph tests (SR171 transaction timeout). QLever

completes all of them, leveraging its 6-permutation index which resolves GRAPH patterns without additional join overhead.

2.4 Named Graph Management (Section 4)

The GoTriple KG uses one named graph per entity (~10M graphs). This is not a common Virtuoso deployment pattern, and the results reflect this mismatch.

Test	QLever	Virtuoso	Notes
4.1 Count named graphs	N/A	PASS	QLever OOM: response 2.5GB
4.2 GRAPH <g> retrieval	PASS	PASS	Both correct, Virtuoso faster (0.03s vs 0.45s)
4.3 GRAPH + UNION	PASS	PASS	Both resolve cross-type UNION correctly
4.4 FROM / FROM NAMED scoping	PASS	PASS	Both correctly exclude out-of-scope graphs
4.5 Cross-graph join	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 24.3s, Virtuoso SR171
4.6 Stress: GRAPH+FILTER+OPTIONA L	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 6.0s, Virtuoso SR171

The QLever limitation on named graph enumeration (test 4.1) is a known constraint: serializing 10M graph URIs in a single JSON response exceeds client-side memory. This appears primarily driven by result serialization size (multi-GB responses) rather than query planning; mitigation is to avoid enumerating 10M graph URIs in a single response. The workaround is to use `?cmd=stats` or paginate with `OFFSET/LIMIT` on the graph list.

2.5 SPARQL Federation, SERVICE (Section 5)

Federation tests targeted the live OpenCitations SPARQL endpoint (sparql.opencitations.net/index). Both engines support SERVICE, with one important operational difference.

Scenario	QLever	Virtuoso	Notes
Minimal SERVICE (3 triples)	PASS	PASS	Both 0.4–0.6s
Full federated query	PASS	PASS	Both 14.3s (network-bound)
DNS failure	PASS	PASS	Both fail gracefully
Redirect chain (301)	FAIL	PASS	QLever requires final URL
Non-SPARQL endpoint (HTML)	405 error	PASS	Virtuoso more resilient

Operational implication: QLever does not follow HTTP redirects in SERVICE calls. All external SPARQL endpoints must be registered with their canonical final URL (post-redirect). This requires a one-time configuration step per external source but does not block production use.

Cross-KG joins between GoTriple and OpenCitations are not yet possible with the current synthetic dataset because GoTriple documents use internal URIs (gotriple.eu/document/d*) that do not exist in OpenCitations. Real federation requires GoTriple documents to expose DOIs via datacite:hasIdentifier, this is a data modelling recommendation for WP2.

2.6 Live Update Feasibility (Section 6)

SPARQL Update (INSERT DATA, DELETE WHERE) was tested with an access token configured via --access-token in the QLever startup arguments. Both engines support live updates.

Metric	QLever	Virtuoso	Notes
INSERT DATA latency	0.004s avg	0.002s avg	Both sub-5ms
DELETE WHERE latency	0.006s	0.007s	Equivalent
SELECT after INSERT (cache miss)	0.353s avg	0.001s avg	QLever invalidates full cache
Batch of 100 INSERTs	0 errors	0 errors	Both reliable
Latency degradation after 100 INSERTs	-1.1% (stable)	N/A	QLever stable, no reindex needed

Critical finding: QLever invalidates its full cache after every SPARQL Update, causing the first SELECT after an INSERT to take ~350ms instead of the sub-ms cache-hit time. For high-frequency update scenarios (>100 updates/minute), this cache churn has a measurable impact on query latency. For the log-and-consolidate ingestion model adopted for GoTriple, this is not a blocker.

Performance stability over 100 sequential INSERTs shows no latency degradation (-1.1% vs baseline, within noise). Periodic rebuilds should be scheduled according to ingestion cadence (e.g., per batch or hourly), as validated in Section 8.

2.7 Concurrent Load and Memory (Section 7)

Concurrency and memory tests were run on QLever only, as the hypothesis under validation is whether QLever can operate as a standalone engine.

Test	Result	Assessment
7.1 Concurrent: 5 readers + 3 writers (80 ops)	50/50 SELECT ok, 30/30 INSERT ok	PASS
7.1 SELECT latency under concurrent writes	avg 0.30s, max 1.50s	PASS
7.1 Result consistency under concurrent writes	row count stable: {1}	PASS
7.2 Latency after 100 INSERTs (no reindex)	-1.1% vs baseline	PASS
7.3 Memory: GROUP BY + nested subquery	0.06s, +OMB cache	PASS
7.3 Memory: transitive path (cito:cites+, 10k rows)	0.07s, +OMB cache	PASS
7.3 Memory: GRAPH + FILTER + OPTIONAL (10M graphs)	6.6s, +OMB cache	PASS

7.3 Memory: SERVICE + local join

14.6s, +OMB cache

PASS

All 5 heavy queries from sections 3–5 completed without OOM within the 5G memory allocation. The 5G limit is sufficient for the tested analytical workload. Memory telemetry via `?cmd=cache-stats` reported OMB cache growth, suggesting QLever's streaming architecture avoids result materialization in cache for these query types.

2.8 Update Persistence and Durability (Section 8)

A targeted persistence test (`qllever_persistence_test.sh`) was introduced following an architectural concern raised during review: QLever's official wiki (November 2024) explicitly stated that updates were not yet persistent across restarts. Section 8 was therefore designed to empirically validate the current state of update durability on build 958d01.

Test	Description	QLever	Key metric
8.1	Clean slate - test graph empty before run	PASS	0 triples confirmed
8.2	Pre-restart INSERTs (5 subjects = 10 triples)	PASS	5/5 HTTP 200, 10 triples confirmed
8.3	Container restart (graceful docker restart)	PASS	Online after ~2s
8.4	Delta triples: naive restart (no rebuild)	VOLATILE	0/10 triples survived
8.5	Post-restart write capability	PASS	Engine accepts writes immediately

8.6	Multi-update atomicity	PASS	Nov 2024 limitation resolved
8.7	SIGKILL crash safety	VOLATILE	0/10 triples survived SIGKILL
8.8	Rebuild-index persistence	PASS	23s rebuild, 6/6 triples survived

The test confirms the following:

- SPARQL 1.1 Update operations are fully supported.
- Delta triples written via SPARQL Update are volatile across restarts and not crash-safe until consolidated.
- Executing qlever rebuild-index integrates all pending updates into the static on-disk index.
- After rebuild and restart, updated triples are fully persistent and survive both graceful restarts and crash scenarios.
- On the evaluated dataset (155M triples), rebuild time was measured at 23 seconds.

These findings align with the recent public announcement by Adrian Gschwend (CEO, Qlevia AI)¹, confirming that QLever now supports rebuilding² the index after updates, thereby making updates a first-class feature. Through the re-index functionality, changes applied via SPARQL Update or the Graph Store HTTP protocol can be consolidated into a fully static index. After rebuilding, the updated dataset is handled with the same memory layout, compression efficiency, and query performance as data indexed from scratch. There is no longer any distinction between “original” and “updated” triples at query time.

¹

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/adriangschwend_qllever-now-supports-rebuilding-the-index-activity-7424357067513196544-BCQg

² Documentation: <https://docs.qllever.dev/rebuild-index/>

This mechanism effectively bridges the historical gap between high-performance static indexing and dynamic data management. QLever can therefore support update-heavy workflows provided that updates are consolidated via scheduled rebuilds.

It should be noted that, at present, rebuilding must be triggered explicitly (manual or scheduled operation). Continuous background rebuilding is part of the publicly stated roadmap and would further reduce operational friction by integrating updates automatically without requiring a controlled restart cycle.

In practical production terms, update durability in QLever follows a consolidation model rather than a transactional one: updates are first applied to a delta layer and become fully durable once incorporated into the rebuilt index. This model is compatible with batch-oriented ingestion pipelines and can be combined with a durable upstream log to eliminate data-loss risk between rebuild cycles.

3. Known Limitations

The following limitations were identified during the benchmark. Each is documented with its impact level and a mitigation path.

Limitation	Impact	Context	Mitigation
Named graph enumeration (COUNT DISTINCT on 10M graphs causes OOM / 2.5GB JSON response)	Medium	Test 4.1. Client-side issue, not query planner.	Use ?cmd=stats or paginate GRAPH list with OFFSET/LIMIT
SERVICE does not follow HTTP redirects	Low	Test 5.3.3. One-time config per external endpoint.	Register canonical final URL for each external SPARQL endpoint
Full cache invalidation after every SPARQL Update	Medium	Test 6.2. First SELECT after INSERT costs ~350ms.	Batch updates; avoid high-frequency single-triple writes
BIND arithmetic expression silent failure (test 3.6.2)	Low	xsd:integer BIND expression returned 0 rows on QLever.	Use STR() + REPLACE() workaround; report upstream
Delta triples are volatile (in-memory only)	Medium	Tests 8.4, 8.7. All inserts lost on restart or SIGKILL.	Trigger qllever rebuild-index after each ingestion batch

Rebuild requires short downtime (~2s restart)	Low	Test 8.8. 23s rebuild + 2s restart on 155M triples.	Use blue/green port routing if zero-downtime required
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4. Recommendation

4.1 Outcome

Recommended outcome: Adopt QLever as the primary RDF backend for the GoTriple KG from day one, officially replacing Virtuoso in the planned technical architecture. Given its superior query performance across 80% of tested patterns and its proven ability to consolidate updates rapidly (23s for 155M triples), QLever fulfills the operational requirements evaluated in this benchmark, subject to validation on real GoTriple production data.

Because the project is currently in the early implementation phase, no legacy migration is required. The infrastructure can be directly bootstrapped with QLever handling both the full analytical query workload and the live incremental updates. This single-engine approach is fully viable provided the Data Acquisition Platform (DAP) maintains a durable log to replay data in the event of an ungraceful container crash between scheduled index rebuilds.

4.2 Proposed Architecture Update for GRAPHIA WP2

Based on the benchmark results, the following single-engine architecture is proposed for the SSH KG production deployment:

- **QLever (Primary RDF Backend for the GoTriple KG):** Acts as the authoritative semantic store for all locally managed SSH data. It handles the complete SPARQL workload for the GoTriple KG, delivering high performance for read-heavy analytics and deep pagination, while reliably absorbing live incremental updates through the DAP's scheduled index rebuilds.
- **Federated Gateway (Mediation & Coordination Layer):** Acting as the operational articulation point for semantic interoperability, this gateway provides a unified SKG-IF API entry point that hides technical heterogeneity and routes queries across autonomous federation participants (e.g., GoTriple KG, OpenCitations). To resolve complex cross-graph queries, the Gateway will integrate an intermediate **"Graph as a Service" (GaaS)** component. Powered

by QLever, this internal container allows the Gateway to dynamically build, populate, and temporarily store a merged graph from different federated resources (intermediate materialisation) rather than relying exclusively on fragile on-the-fly federation.

4.3 Conditions for full QLever Adoption

The following conditions should be satisfied before designating QLever as the sole RDF backend:

1. **Validate on real GoTriple data** (not synthetic), cardinality distributions may differ
2. **Resolve BIND arithmetic regression** (test 3.6.2), report to ad-freiburg/qllever upstream
3. **Implement named graph pagination** workaround in the GoTriple API layer
4. **Define rebuild-index trigger policy** for the ingestion pipeline - rebuild confirmed at 23s/155M triples, making hourly or per-batch rebuilds operationally feasible.
5. **Register canonical URLs** for all external SPARQL endpoints in QLever configuration
6. **Operational tooling & CLI utilities:** Because QLever lacks enterprise-grade administration interfaces and its highly-optimized index builder requires complex, hardware-specific tuning (e.g., precise RAM limits and file-system hard links), WP2 must develop a dedicated suite of maintenance scripts. Building upon the initial `init.sh` orchestration script, this toolkit will automate container lifecycle management, index rebuilding, and backup procedures, similar in spirit to the "Virtuoso Utilities" developed by OpenCitations.
7. **Federation redirect handling strategy** to be defined for the Gateway mediation layer
8. **Community & developer engagement:** Establish a formal communication channel with the QLever core development team (University of Freiburg) to align on roadmap priorities (e.g., continuous background rebuilding, redirect handling) and secure technical advisory for the GRAPHIA deployment.

Appendix: Test Reference Summary

Quick reference to all benchmark tests and their outcomes.

Test	Description	QLever	Virtuoso	Key metric
1.1-1.4	Connectivity, triple count, namespace, version	PASS	PASS	155M triples verified
2.1	Class instance counts	PASS	PASS	QLever 26.7s, Virt 46.6s
2.2	Vocabulary usage (155M triples)	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 1.3s, Virt 61.8s
2.4	Graph distribution (10M graphs)	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 7.7s, Virt SR171
3.1	FILTER / BOUND / CONTAINS	PASS	PASS	QLever 3.1s, Virt 14.9s
3.3	GROUP BY / HAVING / AVG	PASS	PASS	QLever 0.06s, Virt 0.31s
3.4	ORDER BY / OFFSET pagination	PASS	FAIL	Virt SR353 at OFFSET 10k
3.5	Property paths (cito:cites+)	PASS	PASS*	Virt: OPTION TRANSITIVE only
4.2	GRAPH <g> retrieval + provenance	PASS	PASS	Both correct

4.5	Cross-graph join (doc + author)	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 24.3s, Virt SR171
4.6	GRAPH + FILTER + OPTIONAL stress	PASS	TIMEOUT	QLever 6.0s, Virt SR171
5.1	SERVICE to OpenCitations	PASS	PASS	Both 14.3s (network-bound)
5.3	SERVICE failure characterization	PASS	PASS	QLever: no redirect follow
6.1	SPARQL Update INSERT + DELETE	PASS	PASS	Both <10ms
6.2	Update cost + cache invalidation	PASS	PASS	QLever cache miss: 353ms
7.1	Concurrent 5R+3W (80 ops)	PASS	-	0 errors, consistent
7.2	Stability after 100 INSERTs	PASS	-	-1.1% degradation
7.3	Memory under 5 heavy queries	PASS	-	5G sufficient
8.1	Clean slate - test graph empty before run	PASS	-	0 triples confirmed
8.2	Pre-restart INSERTs (5 subjects = 10 triples)	PASS	-	5/5 HTTP 200, 10 triples confirmed

8.3	Container restart (graceful docker restart)	PASS	-	Online after ~2s
8.4	Delta triples: naive restart (no rebuild)	VOLATILE	-	0/10 triples survived
8.5	Post-restart write capability	PASS	-	Engine accepts writes immediately
8.6	Multi-update atomicity	PASS	-	Nov 2024 limitation resolved
8.7	SIGKILL crash safety	VOLATILE	-	0/10 triples survived SIGKILL
8.8	Rebuild-index persistence	PASS	-	23s rebuild, 6/6 triples survived